

FOOD CONTAMINATION AND SAFETY TRAINING AS PREDICTORS OF FOOD SAFETY PRACTICES AMONG FOOD HANDLERS

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ABSTRACT

Higher levels of food safety practices among SME food handlers are continuously correlated with a solid foundation in food contamination knowledge and comprehensive food safety training, highlighting the significance of ongoing investment in food safety education. This descriptive correlational study aimed to determine the significant relationship between the extent of SME food handlers' knowledge on food contamination and food safety training in their food safety practices. The participants included 169 food handlers from Carrascal, Surigao del Sur, Philippines, and were surveyed using a questionnaire that underwent validation and reliability testing. Results revealed that participants had a very high level of knowledge about food contamination across biological, physical, and chemical factors. Their extent of food safety training is very high. The participants demonstrated a very high level of food safety practices across personal hygiene, food preparation and cooking, and food service. Food safety training positively correlated with overall food safety practices, particularly in personal hygiene, food preparation, and cooking. A moderate positive correlation was found between knowledge about contamination and food safety practices, while the correlation between training and food service practices was relatively weaker. Consistent investment in food safety training programs is consequently required. It improves individual competency, promotes responsible handling habits, and eventually leads to safer food systems and better public health outcomes. Future research may replicate and expand the study to include several geographic regions and types of food establishments, such as informal food sectors, franchised outlets, and rural-based SMEs.

Keywords: *Food, Contamination, Safety Training, Safety Practices, SME, Food Handlers*

INTRODUCTION

Food safety is a global concern because of its serious impact on health and the economy (Garcia et al., 2020; Garcia et al., 2020). The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that unsafe food causes about 600 million cases of foodborne illness each year and around 420,000 deaths worldwide (Oduoye et al., 2024; Owusu-Apenten & Vieira, 2023; Pires & Devleesschauwer, 2021). This situation highlights the need for effective food safety measures, especially in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) that often face problems like limited resources, poor infrastructure, and weak enforcement of safety standards (Kabiesz, 2024). In these workplaces, food handlers play an important role in preventing contamination through their knowledge, training, and daily practices (Tuglo et al., 2021).

Food contamination is caused by different types of hazards—biological, chemical, and physical (Garvey, 2019; Singh et al., 2019). Biological hazards such as Salmonella, E. coli, and viruses are common causes of foodborne diseases (Abebe et al., 2020; Gourama, 2020). Chemical hazards include pesticide residues and cleaning chemicals, while physical hazards come from objects like metal or glass (Lebelo et al., 2021; Onyeaka, 2023). Many cases of contamination happen because food handlers lack knowledge about these dangers (da Silva Cota et al., 2023). This is especially true in SMEs, where food safety measures are not strictly followed. Even though research shows that knowledge affects food safety behavior (Odipe et al., 2019; Sanlier & Baser, 2020), many food handlers still lack awareness and understanding of the risks (da Silva Cota et al., 2023).

Training is one way to improve food safety in the workplace. It helps food handlers learn proper hygiene, how to avoid cross-contamination, and how to control food temperature (Insfran-Rivarola et al., 2020a; Odipe et al., 2019; Nyawo et al., 2021). Studies show that trained food handlers usually perform better in terms of hygiene and safety (Insfran-Rivarola et al., 2020; Taha et al., 2021; Zenbaba et al., 2022). Training also reduces their anxiety when working and helps them understand why food safety rules matter. However, it is not always easy to keep the lessons learned from training, especially when workers are older or have been doing their jobs a long time. Regular and good-quality training is needed, but many SMEs cannot afford it or do not have the time and support to do it (Parast & Safari, 2022; Signoretti, 2020).

Food safety practices include actions like washing hands, using clean utensils, cooking food properly, and storing it at the right temperature (Kamboj et al., 2020; Islam et al., 2022). Research shows that food handlers who have received education and training tend to follow these safety steps more closely (Insfran-Rivarola et al., 2020). Still, even trained workers sometimes do not follow safety rules because of problems at work like lack of time, weak supervision, or poor work culture. For example, Jevšnik and Raspor (2021) found that food samples still had bacteria even when workers said they followed hygiene rules, which means having knowledge is not always enough to keep food safe.

Most of the past studies focus only on food safety knowledge or practice. Very few have studied how food contamination knowledge, safety training, and food safety practices are related to each other, especially in the context of SMEs in developing countries. This is an important gap because SMEs in many countries—do not always have access to training programs or strict inspections (Fajarwaty & Jukes, 2022). In Surigao del Sur, there is very little local research or data that looks at what food handlers know, how they are trained, and how they practice food safety. Some food businesses in the region are allowed to operate even if they do not meet proper safety standards, which increases the risk of foodborne diseases.

This study looked into the food contamination knowledge, safety training experience, and food safety practices of food handlers working in SMEs in Surigao del Sur. It aimed to give helpful information that can support planning of training programs, safety policies, and local food safety monitoring systems. The findings may also be useful for local governments, business owners, and health agencies in improving food safety efforts.

The study also supports the goals of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It is especially connected to SDG 3: Good Health and Well-being, which includes reducing sickness and death from unsafe food and harmful chemicals. The research also contributes to SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth, by helping SMEs become safer and more reliable workplaces. Finally, it aligns with SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production, which includes improving food safety along the supply chain. Understanding food handlers' roles in keeping food safe can support long-term improvements in health and sustainable development in the local setting.

Research Questions

The study determined if the extent of knowledge on food contamination of the SME's engaged in food business had a significant correlation in their food safety practices. Specifically, this investigation answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of knowledge on food contamination of the SMEs engaged in food businesses in terms of the following aspects:
 - 1.1 biological;
 - 1.2 physical; and
 - 1.3 chemical?
2. What is the participants' extent of food safety training?
3. What is the extent of food safety practices of the SMEs engaged in food businesses in terms of:
 - 3.1 Personal hygiene;
 - 3.2 Food preparation and cooking; and,
 - 3.3 Food service?
4. Are the food handlers' knowledge on food contamination and food safety training significantly associated their food safety practices?

METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted in Carrascal, Surigao del Sur, Philippines. The study focused on the small and medium enterprise (SME) food service industry in the area.

The study involved 169 food handlers and food-handling supervisors. This selection of the participants was made by a complete enumeration based on the specific inclusion criteria in order to collect reliable and relevant data. All participants must hold a current health certification by the Department of Health (DOH), have food safety training, as well as, at least one year of experience in the food industry. Administrative staff, cashiers, maintenance workers, and owners not directly involved in food preparation were not included in the sample. Sample size was calculated using the Taro Yamane formula for a total population of 290 food handlers, sufficient to provide a strong statistical representation.

A researcher-made and adapted questionnaire was used to collect the data, which was divided into four main parts. The first part collected demographic and business type-related data. The second section measured knowledge on food contamination, and was taken from the studies of Al-Kandari et al. (2019), Akabanda et al. (2017), Kunadu et al. (2016), and Webb & Morancie (2015). The third part was a food safety training knowledge checklist developed by the researchers in accordance with the standard training criteria. The fourth section that focused on food safety practices was modified from Amaich et al. (2024) and consisted of personal hygiene, food handling, and food service compliance. In order to achieve linguistic accessibility and interpretation accuracy, all instruments were translated into Surigaonon-Visayan.

Content validity of the instruments was performed by three food safety and public health specialists. The feedback of these validators was used to refine and enhance the tools for simplicity and congruity with the research questions. A pilot test was performed with 30 non-participating food handlers to establish reliability. Cronbach's Alpha for knowledge on food contamination—biological (0.738), physical (0.721), and chemical (0.817), food safety training (0.944); and personal hygiene (0.831), food preparation (0.928) and food service (0.859) were identified. These findings suggest good internal consistency for each component of the instrument.

Ethical approval was sought from the Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee before the data collection. Permits were also obtained from the Municipal Mayor's Office and the Municipal Health Office. Data collection was conducted during the months of February-March, 2025. The participants were informed in detail about the study's aim, and informed consent was also received prior to the survey. Confidentiality, voluntary participation and the right to withdraw were assured, and ethical considerations of the Belmont Report were adhered to. The questionnaires were completed face-to-face with the help of the researchers. Data retrieval followed and responses were encoded and analyzed using SPSS.

Mean and standard deviation were employed to interpret the knowledge, training,

and food safety practice. The demographic data were described using frequency and percentage distribution. Relationship between variables correlations between variables were investigated using Spearman's Rho correlation to establish significant relationships between the variables, including knowledge of food contamination and food safety practices and food safety training and food safety practices.

This study was limited only to SMEs of Carrascal, Surigao del Sur and focused on the food handlers who were directly involved in food preparation and service. Thus, the results may not be generalizable to other establishments or those outside the premise of the study.

RESULTS

Extent of Knowledge on Food Contamination in terms of Biological, Physical, and Chemical

Table 1 reveals the level of knowledge among the participants with regard to food contamination in three factors. The results showed an overall high level of knowledge (M = 9.33, SD = 0.65). Of the three domains, participants showed the highest level of knowledge in the chemical factor (M = 9.89, SD = 0.40), followed by physical factor (M = 9.15, SD = 1.10). Biological factor (M = 8.96, SD = 1.14) was rated as a high. Although all mean score are in the upper region of the scale, the lowest average and the highest standard deviation at the level of the biological domain imply a wider spread of scoring and a room for improvement in knowledge concerning microbial contamination.

Table 1. Participant's Extent of Knowledge on Food Contamination in terms of Biological, Physical, and Chemical

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Biological	8.96	High	1.14
Physical	9.15	Very High	1.10
Chemical	9.89	Very High	0.40
Overall	9.33	Very High	0.65

Participant's Extent of Food Safety Training

Table 2 shows participants' extent of food safety training. Results show that 65.68% of them reported a very high level of training, while 32.54% indicated a high level. Only 1.78% fell within the moderate level of training. The overall mean score of 4.61 corresponds to a very high interpretation. This findings suggest that participants are well-trained food handlers which enhance their capacity to implement effective and efficient food handling practices and contamination control measures. The small deviation of 0.46 also showcases the consistency between participant's reported responses.

Table 2. Extent of Food Safety Training

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	111	65.68%
3.51-4.50	High	55	32.54%
2.51-3.50	Moderate	3	1.78%
1.51-2.50	Low	0	0.00%
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.00%
Total		169	100.0
Overall Mean Interpretation		4.61	Very High
SD		0.46	

Food Safety Practices

Table 3 presents the extent of food safety practices of the participants across the three dimensions. The mean score of 4.83 (SD = 0.27) indicates a very high good practice in terms of food safety. The highest average among the three domains was food service (M = 4.86, SD = 0.23), closely followed by food preparation and cooking (M = 4.82, SD = 0.31), and personal hygiene (M = 4.81, SD = 0.32). The high scores in all categories are evidence that participants do not just have the mere theoretical knowledge, but are able to apply those into their daily work life in food handling. The small standard deviation also indicates high agreement among them with respect to food safety practices.

Table 3. Food Safety Practices

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Personal hygiene	4.81	Very High	0.32
Food preparation and cooking	4.82	Very High	0.31
Food Service	4.86	Very High	0.23
Overall	4.83	Very High	0.27

Correlation among Food Handlers' Knowledge on Food Contamination and Food Safety Training and their Relationship to Food Safety Practices

Table 4 presents the Spearman Rho correlation between food handlers' knowledge on food contamination, food safety training and food safety practices. The results show a number of statistically significant positive relationships. Interestingly, food safety training is most highly associated with all three food safety practice domains, personal hygiene ($r = .660, p < .01$), food preparation and cooking ($r = .536, p < .01$), and food service ($r = .400, p < .01$). This means that training is of utmost importance in the development of safe practices of food handlers. Additionally, food safety training is positively related to all food safety practices ($r = .606, p < .01$), confirming its vital role in adhering to safety measures.

In terms of knowledge, biological knowledge was significantly associated with food preparation and cooking ($r = .264, p < .01$), personal hygiene ($r = .191, p < .05$), and food safety practices ($r = .179, p < .05$). Physical contamination was also highly associated with personal hygiene ($r = .258, p < .01$), food preparation and cooking ($r = .187, p < .05$), and food safety practices ($r = .211, p < .01$). However, knowledge of chemical contamination did not have significant correlation with food safety practices.

In addition, knowledge of food contamination was positively correlated with personal hygiene ($r = .327, p < .01$), food preparation and cooking ($r = .313, p < .01$), and food safety practices ($r = .281, p < .01$).

Table 4. Spearman's Rho Correlation among Food Handlers' Knowledge on Food Contamination and Food Safety Training and their Relationship to Food Safety Practices

		Biological	Physical	Chemical	Knowledge of Food Contamination	Food Safety Training
Personal Hygiene	Correlation Coefficient	.191*	.258**	.125	.327**	.660**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.017	.001	.119	.000	.000
Food Preparation and cooking	Correlation Coefficient	.264**	.187*	.137	.313**	.536**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.019	.088	.000	.000
Food Service	Correlation Coefficient	.000	.121	.042	.067	.400**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.997	.131	.604	.408	.000
Food Safety Practices	Correlation Coefficient	.179*	.211**	.101	.281**	.606**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.025	.008	.210	.000	.000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

DISCUSSION

SME food handlers exhibit high levels of knowledge towards food contamination, specifically in chemical and physical factors. This is most likely be attributed to the visible properties of these hazards as well as generic training typically provided by regulatory agencies. Chemical hazards are normally labelled and have use protocols to mitigate their exposure, thus reducing the difficulty for handlers to identify and mitigate these contamination. Likewise, physical contaminants are visible to the naked eye to ensure instant identification and removal during the manufacture or inspection of food. Combined with routine workplace reminders and safety audits, and basic hazard awareness programs, these factors increase comfort level and skill level with both chemical and physical threats to food safety. However, knowledge on biological contamination in SME food handlers is somewhat less coherent, perhaps due to the often complex and transparent nature of microbial hazards such as bacteria, viruses and parasites. These

toxic agents are not limited to knowledge of hygiene and sanitation, but have to do with temperature control, cross contamination, and the incubation of microorganisms. Regrettably, not all SMEs have access to training materials, microbiological testing, and/or trained food safety personnel that can prevent them from developing expertise. The findings are supported by existing studies that food handlers have higher knowledge in the areas that are highly regulated or stressed in formal education. Muncke et al. (2020) described how chemical threats often gain prominence within formalized food safety programmes because they are regulated and their effects can be long term. Also, biological agents, which are a primary source of foodborne disease, are often neglected or underestimated by food service employees since they're less tangible (Jevšnik Raspor, 2022). Ehuwa et al. (2021) highlighted that food handlers need reinforcement for knowledge to be retained and applied effectively with regards to biological contamination and it should be repeated and contextualised in training. These studies highlight the necessary to improve training by providing a balanced exposure toward learning content in all areas of contamination, to harmonize education efforts with the risk profile in the real-world food environment to achieve practical and holistic competency in food safe processing.

SME food handlers have a commendable extent of food safety training, which equates to adequate preparation and the knowledge to perform safe food handling. This is a significant aspect of public health, especially in SMEs where operational constraints may often limit access to advanced resources or technology. The lack of variation in the responses of the participants also enhances the reliability of their reported training levels and indicates that food safety is not a fringe occurrence but a practiced standard among SMEs. Moreover, this intensive education may be the reasons for SME food handlers' adoption and sustenance of preventive measures for contamination, and application of standard methods, and response to food safety issues. SMEs are usually found, such training contributes towards workforce competence, meeting regulatory requirements and ultimately building consumer confidence. Moreover, the uniformity of training results indicates that institutional intervention (presumably through LGUs or regulatory bodies) is effective in delivering food safety training. This result is consistent with the existing literature. For example, Insfran-Rivarola et al. (2020) and Taha et al. (2021) reported significantly improved hygiene and contamination control practices among food handlers with training. Further, Limon (2021) reported that training programs certified by the Department of Health (DOH) are significantly related to increased knowledge and regular practice in personal hygiene and prevention of cross-contamination. These programs, which are implemented frequently with local government units (LGUs), are also found to overcome the constraints faced by SMEs in their context offering place-based, adaptive, and repeatable training (Sarmiento & Apritado, 2021; Tuglo et al., 2021). Moreover, the Health Belief Model (HBM) and Knowledge-Attitude-Practice (KAP) theory account for how prior knowledge modification, through intensified training, can influence food handlers' risk perception and self-efficacy levels, ultimately leading to better behavioral outcomes (Alyafei & Easton-Carr, 2025; Baba & Esfandiari, 2023). Hence, the consistency of feeding outcomes across SMEs despite the differences in training received provided evidence of institution's intervention as it can imply that the regulatory bodies and LGUs were effective in nudging them to be competent with their employees, comply

with the food safety laws of the country, and encourage the public to patronize locally owned food establishments (Opina-Tan & Hamoy, 2004; Aquino et al., 2021).

The results suggest that food handlers of SMEs have high level of safety practices, particularly food service, preparation and cooking, and personal hygiene. These imply that they are well-informed with more of practical cooking and serving to meet consumers' demands. This performance indicates the success of past food safety education, engagement in focused training curricula, and experiential industry learning. This was corroborated by the uniform high level of compliance across the sectors, which suggests a culture of compliance that could be strengthened through regular training programs, regulatory enforcement and institutional support from local government units or partner agencies. Standardization is particularly important in the context of SMEs, as the available resources in terms of infrastructure and training is generally much more restricted. Finally, the findings suggest a proactive food safety culture where handlers are more cognizant and adhere to Good Sanitary Practices and are receptive to new issues of food safety. Such operational maturity is imperative for small food businesses in which small slip-ups can result in large public health and economic burdens thus ensuring that food safety principles are applied consistently and competently is a vital safety net.

The results are supported by studies and literature. Insfran-Rivarola et al. (2020) and Taha et al. (2021) demonstrated, for example, that food handlers who were trained in structured manner had robustly more positive attitudes and were more compliant with hygiene and sanitation compared to those who were not. In the same vein, Limon (2021) noted that food handlers who had received their training from registered DOH-accredited centers showed a significant increase in compliance in relation to standards on personal hygiene, cross-contamination, and general food practices. The study further corroborates the consistency seen in food safety habits (Aquino et al. (2021) that knowledge, attitudes and safe practices were positively influenced by training. Additionally, the significance of implementing regulations and support from institutions are highlighted by Dayapera et al., (2024). They noted that local interventions and surveillance contribute to the institutionalization of food safety practices. The literature also recognizes that SMEs often face difficulties in resourcing lifelong learning support; however research has indicated that adaptive, locally relevant applications of learning means that even resource poor SMEs have been able to maintain high standards of food safety (Wolde, 2022; Kabiesz, 2024). Finally, Solon (2022) and Sharma et al. (2023) confirm the importance of an active food-safety culture, associated with training and supervision, in order to reduce the risks of contamination, especially in small companies that tolerate little margin for error.

Results reveal that food safety training has significantly a positive correlation consistently in all domains of safe food practices. It shows that training is one of the leading factors to help the food handlers to practice their activities under safety conditions. The high correlation coefficients imply that training not only provides required information, but also enhances the practice and confidence of safe handling behavior. It encourages good behavior and discourages unsafe practices that may not be so

changeable by knowledge alone. The significance of routine, systematic and practical training for sustaining food safety compliances, particularly in SMEs, which may be associated with fewer monitoring activities, is supported by this finding. The study further shows that awareness on food contamination with specific reference to biological and physical contamination is significantly related to food safety practices. Handlers who are aware of ways in which contamination can occur have better performance in hygiene and food preparation practices. It is consistent with the notion that knowledge of health risks leads to safer behaviour. However, the correlation is weaker compared to training, suggesting that while knowledge forms the foundation, it may not always be sufficient to ensure behavioral compliance unless reinforced by practical application and supervision. Chemical contamination was not significantly associated with food safety practices. This could indicate deficiencies in coverage of training, inadequate focus on chemical hazards during routine work, or lack of visible impact of chemical exposure. Since cleaning agents, pesticides and additives are not usually handled by food handlers, more attention should be paid to this area in future training activities.

The findings underscores the importance of food safety training and knowledge in shaping hygienic practices among food handlers. Research consistently shows that well-structured training programs significantly enhance participants' understanding towards foodborne risks and their ability to comply to cleanliness protocols, solely leading to higher compliance with food safety standards (Nik Husain et al., 2016b; Rebouças et al., 2017). This connection between training and improved practices underscores the idea that knowledge is not just an informative but transformative. Training not only delivers theoretical information but also develops practical skills such as frequent handwashing, surface sanitation, and the correct use of protective equipment, resulting this into visible behavioral improvement (McFarland et al., 2019; Tuglo et al., 2021). Moreover, continuous education fosters a culture of safety and responsibility within food service environments (Azanaw et al., 2019; Mathenge et al., 2018). This cultural shift is important, as it is not only equips food handlers with the necessary skills but also incorporates safety as a core value within the organization. When food handlers recognize that their workplace prioritizes food safety, they are more eager to adopt consistent safe practices and influence those behaviors in their peers. Furthermore, an understanding of contamination risks- especially biological and physical-is recognized as a key predictor of safe handling. Educated food handlers are better equipped to sense dangers and take active measures to avoid risks (Al-Jaberi et al., 2023; da Vitória et al., 2021). This underscores that beyond just receiving training, food handlers must also engage in continuous learning and reflection on best safety practices to maintain high safety standards. Other factors influencing knowledge efficacy- such as institutional support, supervision, and favorable environmental conditions-are also critical factors that can improve learning outcomes and practice compliance (Madilo et al., 2023; Rowell et al., 2013). The presence of supportive leadership and resources can enhance the impact of training initiatives, creating a solid framework for food safety. The Knowledge-Attitude-Practice (KAP) framework and Behavioral Change Theory serve as vital foundations for understanding how information shapes attitudes and, solely, behavior (Insfran-Rivarola et al., 2020; Odeyemi, 2016). These theories supports the idea that effective food safety training is not merely about the transmission of information but it also about fostering an

environment where safe practices are both realized and valued. Together, these perspectives emphasize that education and training are important to securing food safety and reducing the contamination risks across diverse food handling contexts.

Conclusions

This study elucidates a complex interplay of food safety knowledge among SME food handlers, and indicates dire necessity of more tailored education in biological contamination. Fundamental instruction appears to be successful in ensuring an awareness of visible and regularly controlled threats, but less so in developing the deeper, scientific skills necessary to mitigate invisible and more complex risks. This gap requires a repositioning of existing education strategies from one that focuses on compliance based on understanding surface requirements, to one more heavily weighted by a risk-based approach to food safety. There is a need to improve microbiological literacy in SME settings, and this goes beyond the scope of human resource development.

This observed consistency in food safety training among SME food handlers reinforces the role of institutional interventions in inculcating safety-focused behaviors across the industry. In settings where operational constraints are a norm, this basic education acts as a means to fill the gap of resource limitations as well an incentive for adherence to appropriate behavior and ethical responsibility. Beyond regulation, when it comes to food safety training in small food businesses, this is not just a legal requirement - it is a key to public health protection, competence in the workplace, and confidence at the till. Support from local government units and regulators will be essential to maintain and expand on this impact, especially as training delivery is aligned to emerging food safety standards and risks.

The good food safety practices of the SME food handlers highlight that the operational culture of the industry had evolved and was influenced both by previous training and practical experience, a continuous engagement with institutions and stakeholders. Such a culture of compliance can strengthen and make more enduring food safety as a fundamental business ethic and not simply a cost of doing business. Good Sanitary Practices in these resource-scarce SME environments protect public health and also enhance the resilience of the sector against the risk of contamination. Therefore, investing in the capacity development for food safety continues to be an important and key policy for consumer protection and the long-term sustainability of small-scale food businesses.

The results confirm that food safety training is the key driver of safe food handling practices in SMEs, while knowledge alone fails to change behaviors and lead to consistent and compliant food handling practices. It is strongly associated in all food safety domains, which emphasizes the importance of experiential and practice-based teaching of compliance behavior. Knowledge to contamination especially biological and physical is helpful and its influence seems secondary to systematic training. It means there is need for knowledge to be operationalized through applied learning for

transformation to take place. The lack of a strong association between knowledge of chemical contamination and safe practices indicates a critical gap in training focus or task relevance and highlights the need to broaden educational content to include underemphasized hazards. In general, this study supports the principle of real-life practical training as an essential component of food safety training programs, particularly in SME settings where regulatory enforcement may be less stringent but the human health consequences remain significant.

Recommendations

SME food handlers should be motivated to be involved in regular food safety training workshops as a means to update their knowledge in biological, physical and chemical contamination of food. The results, showing relatively lower knowledge on biological risks, suggest that specific training modules need to be focused on foodborne pathogens, temperature danger zones, and cross-contamination prevention. Moreover, they must be offered specific training sessions on new chemical hazards highlighting the necessity of a rational strategy of risk analysis at each step of food handling, preparation, and service. There should also be collaboration with interested parties such as local health bodies and academia for access to the latest research, certification programs and standards updates. Such partnerships will equip handlers with the necessary tools available to harmonize practices with national and international food safety standards and will contribute to a compliance culture and support the professionalization of the SME food sector.

Food businesses play an important role to institutionalize food safety and are encouraged to develop their own training programs for the specific types of risks that come from biological, physical and chemical contamination. Internal quality control mechanisms (e.g., regular audits, spot checks and staff performance assessments) can contribute to improved monitoring and accountability. The access to adequate infrastructure, like handwashing and temperature controlled storage, appropriate working space, equipment for food preparation is equally important to ensure hygiene. Utilizing tech innovations such as digital temperature monitors, metal detectors, and automatic sanitation tools can also bring higher efficiencies to operations and greater precision to food safety. Operators should be in a position to comply with existing mandated regulations such as HACCP, GMP, DOH and Municipal Health Office protocols and should also work for strategic relationship with public health agencies and academic institutions. Thus, food safety should be incorporated within the strategic objectives of the establishments, included in the operational plans, employee evaluations and long-term sustainability plans.

Future studies may replicate and extend the work to a number of geographical areas and types of food outlets, for example informal food sectors, franchised outlets and rurally based SMEs. Broader studies may also facilitate comparisons and more consistent findings between cultural contexts. Moreover, it is recommended for future studies to utilize mixed methods, which can provide a more in-depth picture of the factors of food safety practices. For instance, qualitative data may be useful for exploring psychological,

organizational, and socio-environmental aspects, which may not be well captured in quantitative data. These types of approaches will help provide a broader perspective of food safety practices and assist in developing interventions to engage and affect change in different food handling populations.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards. Ethical clearance from the Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee was secured before the data collection. Written informed consent was obtained from each study participant after they received a detailed explanation of the study, including the purpose, procedures, risks and benefits. Participation was voluntary and participants had an opportunity to discontinue their participation in the research whenever they wanted to without any penalty. No names or information that could identify any of the participants were used during data processing and reporting. No personal identifiable information were collected and all collected responses were stored in secured places and used for research only. The study intended to protect the welfare of participants in this study, presented little risk and did not impact upon the work of participants. Furthermore, the research maintained academic integrity. There was no plagiarism or data distortion, and conflict of interest. The findings were interpreted in an unbiased manner with the aim to add to the public health and academic discussion.

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